

Church of St. Constantine and Helena, Avdou

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Entry tags: Greece, Religious Group, Byzantine, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Greek Orthodox, Crete, Christian Traditions, Religious Place, Medieval Christianity

The Church of St. Constantine and Helena is located west of the village of Avdou alongside the dam of Aposelemis (completed in 2012). The church, today enclosed by a rubble wall, is slightly elevated above the surrounding olive groves. The hills of the Lassithi plateau are visible to the south of the church. The single nave church, today whitewashed, has a saddle roof exterior and a pointed vault interior. The entrance is framed within a pointed arch with a carved lintel, showing a quatrefoil rosette enclosed by a wreath. The remnants of the image of St. Constantine are still visible in the niche above the lintel. Just below the gable roof are five round indentations suggesting that at some point glazed bowls were immured into the facade of the church. Inside the church, a transverse arch divides the nave into two bays. The wall paintings, although damaged, are still legible. The dome of the sanctuary apse shows Christ Pantocrator above two co-officiating bishops, St. John Chrysostom and St. Basil. Although heavily damaged, it is possible that they flank the Melismos in the center. The triumphal arch surrounding the stone altar shows the Hospitality of Abraham on the upper register followed by the Annunciation in the center register. The deacons, St. Stephen and St. Phanourios flank the apse. In the sanctuary vault, the scenes of the Ascension and the Pentecost are presented on the north and south sides respectively. The Gallery of Saints along the side walls include the images of St. Romanus the Melodist, St. Nicholas, St. Anthony (whose face is damaged), St. Marina and Saints Constantine and Helena. Additional saints, unidentifiable, are presented as busts along the transverse arch. The nave vault includes scenes from both the Christological Cycle and the lives of the titular saints, Saints Constantine and Helena. These scenes include the Finding of the True Cross, the Elevation of the True Cross and, possibly, the Baptism of Constantine. The Christological cycle, although reduced, includes scenes of the Transfiguration, Crucifixion, Anastasis and the Healing of the Blind (an unusual addition considering the reduced cycle presented). The west wall includes the Dormition of the Virgin on the upper part of the wall above the door. The lower register of the west wall, to the left side of the entrance is the standing figure of the Archangel Gabriel, his face completely damaged. To the right of the entrance there is a partially preserved dedicatory inscription which notes that the church was built by the contribution and efforts of the priest Manuel during the reign of John (VIII) Palaiologos (1425-48) on 2 September 6954 (1445) by the hand of Manuel and Ioannis Phokas. Below the dedicatory inscription, albeit in poor condition, are two frames of individual sinners and one frame of Communal Punishments (so heavily damaged that all that can be observed is the red background). Among the individual sinners are both male and female fornicators, snakes coiling around their bodies and biting their genitals, the Thief (of which only his legs survive), and the Sorcerer. The inclusion of St. Phanourios, unusually depicted as a deacon, is indicative of the spread of his cult on the island of Crete during the fifteenth century. Additionally, the quality of the work reflects the art of the major artistic centers of the Byzantine world, especially important considering the proximity of this church to the main capital of the island, Candia (today Heraklion).

Date Range: 1445 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Avdou, Pediada, Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The village of Avdou (Αβδού) is located roughly 33km outside of Heraklion. The church of St. Constantine and Helena is located on the outskirts of the village.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel with a pointed vault interior and a saddle roof exterior.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Worship both by individuals and the community

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saints Constantine and Helena

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Both Saints Constantine and Helena

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

–Other [specify]: Dedicatory inscription notes that the church was built by the contribution and efforts of the priest Manuel

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

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– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

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↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel with a pointed vault interior and a saddle roof exterior.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Worship both by individuals and the community

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saints Constantine and Helena

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Both Saints Constantine and Helena

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

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Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Although the church has been whitewashed there are carved decorations around the entrance.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There are wall paintings inside the church.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include images of Christ in the Christological cycle and the image of Christ Pantocrator.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the wall paintings include standing figures of saints, monks and prophets as well as scenes from the life of the titular saints, Saints Constantine and Helena.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Yes the wall paintings include images of individual sinners.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: There is a dedicatory inscription on the west wall of the church.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There are reliefs carved in stone around the entrance to the church. These are geometric and floral motifs.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The painting cycle reflects standard iconography of the Orthodox Christian faith.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is a large amount of graffiti inscribed into the wall paintings including names, initials and dates.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Scenes of hell on the west wall.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Christ Pantocrator is shown on the apse and there are scenes relating to the Christological cycle and the life of the titular saints.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: plaster, stone

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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Iconography

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↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

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Notes: Christ Pantocrator is shown on the apse and there are scenes relating to the Christological cycle and the life of the titular saints.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with

subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service

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Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

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